

THE EFFECTS OF SUSTAINED SILENT READING (SSR) TO LEARNER'S ATTITUDE TOWARDS READING

Mary Joyce D. Ramos, LPT ¹, Gloria L. Ching, EdD ²

¹ Bagupaye Integrated High School, Mulanay, Quezon Province, Philippines

² Eastern Quezon College Inc., Gumaca, Quezon, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14203408>

ABSTRACT

A positive attitude towards reading is crucial for academic success and lifelong learning. However, many learners perceive reading as an obligation rather than a leisure activity, hindering their engagement and enjoyment. This study aims to investigate the effects of Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) on learners' attitudes towards reading. Utilizing a mixed-method research design, the study examined the impact of SSR implementation on learners' attitudes before and after the intervention. Key findings revealed a significant difference in learners' attitudes towards reading, with SSR proving effective in fostering a more positive attitude. Specifically, SSR promoted greater reading frequency and enhanced perceived reading competence. These findings suggest that SSR serves as a valuable reading intervention program, encouraging a love for reading and fostering a positive reading culture within schools. The study recommends that teachers and schools implement SSR to cultivate a joyful reading experience and enhance learners' overall literacy development.

Keywords: *Sustained Silent Reading, Attitude Towards Reading, Reading Engagement*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is one of the most important aspects that need to be mastered as it is the foundation of learning cross-disciplinary subjects. It plays an important role in improving individual life, and abilities in school, and supporting the development of a country. Good reading provides several benefits, such as better comprehension, wider vocabulary, enhanced critical thinking skills, enhanced analytical skills, improved socialization skills,

memory improvement, etc. Having the ability to read fluently could also give students a better opportunity in their future careers as well (Rintaningrum, 2019).

In addition, Herman et al., (2020) stated that reading is a critical academic skill necessary for success in all educational domains. Effective reading often requires the ability to comprehend a text fully. However, some students perceive reading as an uninteresting activity, viewing it as a waste of time. Consequently, they gain little from the process. Therefore, teachers should employ varied methods to teach reading effectively.

Recent studies affirm the importance of reading habits in developing reading skills in both first language and second-language contexts (Cho & Krashen, 2019). Therefore, it is crucial to provide Filipino learners with ample reading practice to foster both reading habits and, most importantly, reading abilities.

According to Gardiner (2021), students who read independently more frequently perform better academically in English and demonstrate stronger literacy skills. One of the numerous benefits of sustained silent reading programs is the improvement in students' attitudes toward reading. Participants in SSR programs can read daily, choose their own books, and are not required to complete book reports or assessments.

Reading practice provides opportunities to develop word recognition and vocabulary, which are essential for comprehension (Cunningham & Stanovich, 2019). Reading texts in a language other than the reader's native tongue can impact comprehension due to inadequate schemata related to these crucial linguistic elements (Carrell, 2021). The efficiency with which words are read affects the cognitive resources required for understanding. Learners who struggle with word recognition often have difficulty comprehending the material (Perfetti & Stafura, 2021). Thus, reading practice facilitates the acquisition and expansion of vocabulary, which in turn supports reading comprehension. Learners who read voluntarily tend to enhance both their vocabulary and reading fluency.

There is substantial agreement that a positive reading attitude influences reading outcomes positively. However, literature indicates that as students transition to middle or high school, their reading attitudes often decline (McKenna et al., 2021), which can negatively impact their reading achievement and further exacerbate this trend. Since reading is crucial for knowledge acquisition and academic success, it is essential to equip students with vital reading skills. Regular reading activities also enhance general language abilities, including vocabulary, speaking, and communication skills (Cain & Oakhill, 2022). Moreover, developing reading habits and fostering a love of reading promote reading literacy.

The importance of employing effective reading strategies to improve learners' reading abilities and cultivate a love for reading has gained increasing attention in recent years. Alongside popular methods like DEAR (Drop Everything and Read), several alternative reading strategies have emerged, demonstrating their effectiveness in promoting reading engagement and competence. One such alternative is Independent

Reading Time (IRT), which is like DEAR and DIRT. IRT allocates time for students to engage in self-selected reading, allowing them to choose books or materials that align with their interests. This approach fosters enjoyment in reading, supports individual choice, and enhances reading comprehension and fluency.

Another strategy that has garnered attention is Reading Workshops. These structured sessions encompass a range of activities such as guided reading, shared reading, and book discussions. By actively participating in these workshops, students have opportunities to practice reading strategies, engage in meaningful conversations about texts, and receive targeted instruction to enhance their comprehension and critical thinking abilities.

These alternative reading strategies, alongside SSR (Sustained Silent Reading) and DEAR (Drop Everything and Read), have proven effective in improving reading skills, comprehension, and overall enjoyment of reading. Educators can select and adapt these strategies based on the unique needs and interests of their students, creating a dynamic and engaging reading environment that promotes a lifelong love for reading. By examining the impact of these alternative strategies, this study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on effective reading instruction and provide insights for educators seeking to enhance their instructional practices.

Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) is a strategy designed to increase student reading comprehension, based on the principle that the more a student reads, the better their comprehension will be. SSR allocates specific times during the week for students to engage in silent, uninterrupted reading. Through the implementation of SSR, schools can offer students facing reading difficulties the opportunity for free voluntary reading, allowing them to read silently at designated times each day while being guided and monitored by teachers.

Students commonly face several challenges when reading books. First, they may open a book without engaging with the text; they might recite words without grasping the underlying ideas. Second, many students have a limited vocabulary, making it difficult for them to understand the context of what they read. Additionally, reading can be challenging for students who tend to spell out words one by one, hindering their fluency. Lastly, some students find reading boring; when they cannot comprehend the material, they often lose interest and become sleepy.

Reading develops a person's understanding, communication, perceptual skills, and many other abilities. Reading increases one's vocabulary, boosts verbal and cognitive growth, removes achievement disparities, and generally helps one grow and advance in all spheres. (Cunnington and Stanovich, 2019). Despite the proven benefits of reading, many people do not read enough or read regularly, even in developed countries (Gelles-Watnick & Perrin, 2021). In the Philippines, 94% of adults enjoy reading, yet only 17.3% read books daily. Furthermore, most Filipino adults (87%) are not aware of the existence of a library in the barangay (community). On the other hand, 96% of

Filipino children report that they enjoy reading yet read non-school books for only 13.7 hours per month (National Book Development Board [NBDB], 2019).

Many researchers and educators agree that practices along the SSR continuum meaning more time spent reading texts are effective for building vocabulary, improving reading comprehension, enhancing writing ability, increasing background knowledge, and developing schemata (Armstrong et al., 2019).

In the Philippines, the issue of students struggling with reading is not new. Various studies indicate that reading problems among Filipino students appear to be persistent (Alayon, 2019; Habagat & Rizon, 2021; Miguel, 2021; Montalban, 2020; Umali, 2019). As a result, reading and literacy instruction have consistently been top priorities in all Philippine curricula. Although remediation for struggling readers has been implemented in the Philippines for decades, its optimization has gained momentum primarily through Department Order (DO) 45, series of 2002, which established the Reading Literacy Program in Elementary Schools, and DO 27, series of 2005, which introduced Remedial Instruction Programs in High Schools. The latest initiative, DepEd Memorandum No. 001, series of 2024, introduces "Catch-up Fridays" in elementary and secondary schools nationwide. This memorandum designates a specific day for targeted interventions and activities to support students' learning and development.

The Philippines has consistently reported a significant percentage of low performers among all PISA-participating countries and economies, with 80% of Filipino students failing to reach the minimum level of proficiency in reading. Their poor scores in English, Mathematics, and Science have been attributed to a lack of basic reading and comprehension skills. In response, the Department of Education (DepEd) launched the "Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa" (3Bs Initiatives) to intensify advocacy for reading and to commit to ensuring that every learner becomes a proficient reader at their grade level (PISA, 2018). The results of the 2019 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed that only 19.4% of 15-year-olds achieved at least the minimum proficiency level in overall reading literacy (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2019). For the second consecutive time, the Philippines ranked in the bottom 10 out of 81 countries in reading comprehension, although a 6.9% improvement was noted in the 2022 PISA results.

Under the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) law, students are tested in reading and math from grades 3 to 8 and once in high school, with results that must be reported. The law ensures that teachers are highly qualified, requiring them to have a bachelor's degree in their field. Given the significance of assessment, scores are critical for the school's survival, leading educators and administrators to seek resources that can help learners improve their skills in mathematics, writing, and reading.

In response to the educational challenges posed by the pandemic, Mulanay District I has taken proactive steps to address learning gaps and enhance reading skills among students. The district launched a series of reading strategies and interventions specifically designed to cultivate an interest in literature and improve comprehension levels. Despite

these concerted efforts, certain schools continue to face significant challenges in combating illiteracy, notably Bagupaye Integrated High School, which struggles with a high number of non-readers and non-numerate students.

The impact of the pandemic on education cannot be understated, as disruptions to traditional learning models have widened gaps in literacy and numeracy skills. Mulanay District I's initiatives to mitigate these challenges demonstrate a commitment to supporting student learning and academic development. By implementing diverse reading strategies and interventions, the district seeks to bridge the divide created by remote learning and ensure that students receive the necessary support to enhance their reading abilities.

However, despite these commendable efforts, the persistence of non-readers in schools like Bagupaye Integrated High School highlights the complexity of addressing educational disparities. Contributing factors may include inadequate resources and varying levels of academic support within the community. Additionally, unique conditions faced by each institution such as student demographics and local challenges can further impact literacy rates and hinder progress in overcoming literacy obstacles.

Bagupaye Integrated High School's Continuous Improvement Project (CIP) team conducted a study in 2022 to identify the factors affecting students' reading comprehension. Based on their root-cause analysis, the CIP team found that low comprehension levels and frustration with reading stem from negative attitudes and a lack of interest in reading. In response, the team launched the project DREAM (Develop Reading Among Marginalized Learners) to increase the number of independent readers among BIHS students.

These challenges led the researchers to conclude that students are not engaging in enough independent reading. To help Filipino learners develop reading skills and habits, it is crucial to provide them with ample reading practice. Consequently, the researcher decided to develop a study on the effects of Sustained Silent Reading using various reading materials on learners' attitudes toward reading at Bagupaye Integrated High School.

Research Questions

This study examines the effects of Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) on Grade 9 learners' attitudes toward reading.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learner's attitude towards reading before the implementation of Sustained Silent Reading in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Quantitative
 - 1.1.1. Positive Attitude Towards Reading
 - 1.1.2. Negative Attitude Towards Reading
 - 1.2. Qualitative

- 1.2.1 Self and Peer Distraction
 - 1.2.2 Self and Peer Engagement
2. What is the learner's attitude towards reading after the implementation of Sustained Silent Reading in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Quantitative
 - 2.1.1. Positive Attitude Towards Reading
 - 2.1.2. Negative Attitude Towards Reading
 - 2.2. Qualitative
 - 2.2.1 Self and Peer Distraction
 - 2.2.2 Self and Peer Engagement
3. Is there a significant difference in learner's attitudes towards reading before and after the implementation of Sustained Silent Reading using various reading materials?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what implementation plan can be recommended by the researcher to enrich Sustained Silent Reading as a reading intervention program?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design. A mixed-methods research design is a procedure for collecting, analyzing, and integrating both quantitative and qualitative research methods within a single study to understand a research problem. This design offered several benefits for addressing complex research issues as it combined the philosophical frameworks of both post-positivism and interpretivism (Fetters, 2019), interweaving qualitative and quantitative data in a way that meaningfully explained the research issues. It also provided a solid foundation, methodological flexibility, and an in-depth understanding of smaller cases (Maxwell, 2021). In other words, the use of mixed methods enabled researchers to answer research questions with sufficient depth and breadth (Enosh et al., 2019) and helped generalize findings and implications to the broader population.

This research study was conducted during the first and second quarters of the 2024-2025 school year. The researcher aimed to develop a positive attitude towards reading among Grade 9 students using Sustained Silent Reading as an intervention. The study sought to determine the attitudes towards reading of Grade 9 students by administering questionnaires and conducting post-observation before and after the immersion in SSR, as well as to identify significant differences in learners' attitudes towards reading before and after the intervention. The output was an Instructional

Implementation Plan on Sustained Silent Reading, while the outcome was the development of a positive attitude towards reading among Grade 9 learners. To assess the attitudes of Grade 9 learners towards reading before and after implementing SSR, the data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage means, and standard deviation.

Research Locale

Bagupaye Integrated High School served as the site of the study. It was formerly named Bagupaye National High School. Located in Brgy. Bagupaye, Mulanay, Quezon, the primary income of the residents was derived from farming. Mulanay, officially known as the Municipality of Mulanay, is a first-class municipality in the province of Quezon, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it had a population of 55,576 people. Mulanay is situated approximately 100 kilometers (62 miles) southeast of Lucena City. Administratively, the town was subdivided into 28 barangays, four (4) of which were urban areas. Each barangay consisted of puroks, and some had sitios. As of the 2023-2024 school year, there were thirty-five teachers, three non-teaching personnel, five hundred ninety-four students in Junior High School, and two hundred twenty-nine students in Senior High School.

Based on the root cause analysis conducted by the Bagupaye Integrated High School Continuous Improvement Project (CIP) team in 2022, which examined factors affecting learners' reading abilities, the data revealed that the underlying problems for the majority of struggling Grade 9 readers were attributed to poor reading habits. This led to a negative attitude towards reading and a low level of reading comprehension and skills. If a positive attitude towards reading could be developed among learners, it would result in higher levels of reading skills, enabling students to gain knowledge through improved reading comprehension and subsequently achieve better academic performance. Thus, the researcher conducted this study at Bagupaye Integrated High School to support quality education in the context of implementing recovery learning in Mulanay District, Mulanay, Quezon.

Population and Sampling

The researcher used purposive sampling to determine the respondents of the study. The researcher used the results of the PHIL-IRI assessment to identify the number of struggling readers with frustration-level reading abilities as the respondents for this study. Thirty-nine Grade 9 learners under the frustration level of reading skills from Bagupaye Integrated High School in Mulanay, Quezon, were selected as the study's respondents.

The Population of the Study		
Grade 9 Sections	Total Number of Learners	Respondents of the study
Acacia	37	5
Narra	35	11

Yakal	31	14
Mahogany	36	9
Total	139	39

Research Instrument

The instrument for this research was an adapted version of the Rhody Secondary Reading Attitude Assessment, which served as the primary quantitative data-gathering tool. The researcher sent a request letter via email to the author seeking permission to use the Rhody Secondary Reading Attitude Assessment as an instrument for this study. Meanwhile, to gather qualitative data, the researcher used a researcher-made observation guide checklist. The researcher ensured the effectiveness and validity of the instruments through a validation process.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher personally sought permission to conduct the research study from the PSDS of Mulanay District via letter. The researcher also wrote letters to obtain permission from the school head and parents, confirming their agreement to allow their learners to participate in the study.

Following approval, the researcher approached the teachers and school administrators to seek their permission to conduct Sustained Silent Reading (SSR). Four sections of Grade 9 learners at Bagupaye Integrated High School were involved in this study for the school year 2024–2025. After gathering the results of the PHIL-IRI administration, thirty-nine Grade 9 learners under the frustration level of reading skills were selected as the study's respondents.

Before the immersion in SSR, the researcher administered a survey questionnaire to identify the learners' attitudes towards reading. The survey questionnaire evaluated the learners' attitudes towards reading, consisting of 25 questions adapted from the Rhody Secondary Reading Attitude Assessment.

Upon retrieval of the survey questionnaire, the researcher collected the completed questionnaires immediately after the respondents answered the 25 survey questions. After utilizing various reading materials in the implementation of SSR, observations were conducted to determine the attitudes of Grade 9 learners towards reading. Prior to the immersion in SSR, the researcher formulated a guide to implement the strategies.

Immersion of Sustained Silent Reading using Various Reading Materials

One Hour of Student Orientation. Learners were required to attend or watch an in-person orientation about the immersion of Sustained Silent Reading (SSR). The orientation discussed the expected behavior of students during the SSR immersion.

Eight Weeks of Instruction. The SSR immersion consisted of eight weeks of instruction for Grade 9 learners at Bagupaye Integrated High School. Additionally, a survey questionnaire was administered one week before the SSR immersion.

First Week to Eighth Week. A set of various reading materials was provided daily to the Grade 9 learners based on their learning level and grade. Every Friday, the teacher conducted observations to assess the learners' attitudes towards reading each week during the eight-week instruction cycle, using the various reading materials. After the eight weeks of SSR instruction, the survey questionnaire was administered on the last Friday of the eight-week cycle.

Teacher-to-Learner Feedback. Since the interventions were implemented in in-person classes, students received quarterly feedback on their reading development through SSR. This feedback included information about their reading levels and comments from the teacher, designed to serve as systematic reinforcement for the participating students.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In Research Question 1, the learners' attitudes towards reading before the implementation of SSR were identified. The data were analyzed using mean percentage scores, frequency counts, and a scale for reading attitude levels.

Scale for Learners' Positive Attitude Towards Reading

Description	Mean Range	Scale	Interpretation
Disagree	1.00-1.79	1	Very Low Attitude
Partially Agree	1.80-2.59	2	Low Attitude
Agree	2.60-3.39	3	Moderate Attitude
Highly Agree	3.40- 4.19	4	Positive Attitude
Strongly Agree	4.20-5.00	5	High Positive Attitude

Scale for Learners' Positive Attitude Towards Reading

Description	Mean Range	Scale	Interpretation
Disagree	1.00-1.79	5	Very Low Attitude
Partially Agree	1.80-2.59	4	Low Attitude
Agree	2.60-3.39	3	Moderate Attitude
Highly Agree	3.40- 4.19	2	Positive Attitude
Strongly Agree	4.20-5.00	1	High Positive Attitude

In Research Question 2, the collected data were analyzed using frequency counts, mean percentages, and standard deviation to determine the level of learner's attitudes towards reading development before and after the implementation of SSR.

While in Research Question 3, the significant difference between the attitude of learners towards reading before and after implementing Sustained Silent Reading was

tested using Levene's Test. This test helped determine the effectiveness of the SSR intervention in improving learner's attitude towards reading.

RESULTS

Part I. The Attitude Towards Reading of Grade 9 Learners before the implementation of Sustained Silent Reading

Table 1

The Learner's Attitude Towards Reading Before the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading

Reading Attitude (Positive)	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I have a lot of books to read at home.	3.00	Moderate Attitude	9
2. I like to read a book whenever I have free time.	3.03	Moderate Attitude	6
3. I get excited about books I have read.	3.31	Moderate Attitude	4
4. I love to read.	3.74	Positive Attitude	1
5. I like to read books by well-known authors.	3.03	Moderate Attitude	7
6. I like to stay at home and read.	3.00	Moderate Attitude	10
7. I like to read to escape from problems.	3.03	Moderate Attitude	8
8. I like to share books with my friends to read.	3.10	Moderate Attitude	5
9. I generally check out a book and read at the library.	2.51	Low Attitude	12
10. I like to broaden my interests through reading.	3.49	Positive Attitude	3
11. I read a lot.	2.87	Moderate Attitude	11
12. I like to improve my vocabulary through reading so I can use more words.	3.51	Positive	2
13. I like to have books to read.	2.51	Low Attitude	13
Grand Mean	3.09	Moderate Attitude	

As stated in Table, learners generally exhibit a moderate attitude toward reading, as reflected by the grand mean score of 3.09. Among the 13 statements assessing positive reading attitudes, the highest-ranked statement is "I love to read," with a mean score of 3.74, indicating that many learners genuinely enjoy reading. Similarly, statements such as "I like to improve my vocabulary so I can use more words" (mean score of 3.51) and "I like to broaden my interests through reading" (mean score of 3.49) reflect a positive attitude, highlighting the learners' desire to enhance their language skills and expand their knowledge through reading.

However, the majority of the statements, including "I like to read a book whenever I have free time" (mean score of 3.03) and "I like to share books with my friends" (mean score of 3.10), fall under the "Moderate Attitude" category. This suggests that while learners are somewhat engaged with reading, their enthusiasm is not particularly strong. The lowest-scoring items, such as "I generally check out a book when I go to the library" (mean score of 2.51) and "I like to receive books as gifts" (mean score of 2.51), indicate a lack of interest in certain reading-related behaviors, revealing potential areas for improvement.

These data presented a nuanced picture of learners' attitudes toward reading, revealing a generally moderate but not overwhelmingly enthusiastic engagement. The grand mean score of 3.09, falling within the moderate range, sets the overall tone. While this indicates a neither strongly positive nor negative attitude, a closer examination of individual statements reveals a more complex reality. The data highlights a clear enthusiasm among a subset of learners. The high mean score of 3.74 for "I love to read" signifies a genuine enjoyment of reading for a considerable portion of the group.

Similarly, the positive scores for statements emphasizing vocabulary improvement (mean 3.51) and broadening interests (mean 3.49) suggest a recognition of reading's inherent value in personal growth and intellectual development. This suggests a segment of the learners actively values reading for its intrinsic rewards.

However, the majority of statements fall within the "moderate" category, indicating a less fervent engagement. Scores for statements like "I like to read a book whenever I have free time" (mean 3.03) and "I like to share books with my friends" (mean 3.10) point to a somewhat passive engagement. While not negative, these scores suggest that reading isn't a consistently prioritized activity for many learners. The lowest-scoring items, "I generally check out a book when I go to the library" (mean 2.51) and "I like to receive books as gifts" (mean 2.51), are particularly revealing.

These low scores pinpoint potential areas needing attention. They suggest a lack of proactive engagement with reading, indicating that learners may not actively seek out reading opportunities independently. This suggests a need for interventions to stimulate more proactive engagement with reading materials.

In conclusion, the table data suggests a mixed bag of attitudes. While a segment of learners exhibits genuine enthusiasm for reading, a larger group demonstrates a more moderate, passive engagement. The low scores for proactive reading behaviors highlight the need for interventions designed to cultivate a more active and enthusiastic approach to reading. Further investigation into the reasons behind the moderate scores and the low scores on proactive engagement could provide valuable insights for improving reading programs and fostering a stronger love of reading.

Overall, the learners' attitudes toward reading are neither highly positive nor negative. While they express enjoyment in reading and a desire to improve their skills, their actual behaviors such as using library resources or receiving books as gifts suggest a need for further encouragement. Programs like Sustained Silent Reading (SSR), which utilize various reading materials, could be more effective in cultivating a stronger reading culture and fostering positive reading habits among learners.

Table 2*The Learner's Attitude Towards Reading Before the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading (Negative)*

Reading Attitude(negative)	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
14. I feel I have better things to do than read.	3.13	Moderate Attitude	3
15. I seldom buy a book and read.	3.03	Moderate Attitude	5
16. I am willing to tell people that I do not like to read.	2.67	Moderate Attitude	9
17. I never check out a book to read from the library.	2.62	Moderate Attitude	10
18. I seldom read except when I have to do a book report.	3.33	Moderate Attitude	2
19. I think reading is a waste of time.	2.72	Moderate Attitude	7
20. I think reading is boring.	2.77	Moderate Attitude	6
21. I think people are strange when they read a lot.	3.10	Moderate Attitude	4
22. I make fun of people who read a lot.	2.44	Positive Attitude	12
23. I would rather someone tell me information so I won't have to read to get it.	2.69	Moderate Attitude	8
24. I hate reading.	2.56	Positive Attitude	11
25. It takes me a long time to read a book.	3.51	Low Attitude	1
Grand Mean	2.88	Moderate Attitude	

The table presents the learners' negative attitudes toward reading before implementing the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program. The grand mean score of 2.88 suggests a moderate negative attitude toward reading. While the learners do not exhibit extreme aversion to reading, certain negative tendencies are evident, reflecting challenges in cultivating a more positive reading culture.

The highest-ranked statement, "It takes me a long time to read a book," with a mean of 3.51, received a "Positive Attitude" interpretation. This indicates that many learners struggle with reading speed, but they acknowledge this challenge rather than rejecting reading altogether. This could imply that learners perceive reading as time-consuming, which might contribute to their reluctance.

Several statements reflect a moderate negative attitude, such as "I feel I have better things to do than read" with a mean of 3.13, in rank 3, and "I seldom read except when I have to do a book report" with a mean of 3.33, in rank 2, suggesting that many learners view reading as a lower priority or an obligation rather than a pleasurable activity. Additionally, "I think people are strange when they read a lot" with a mean of 3.10, in rank 4, reflects an underlying negative perception of frequent readers, indicating a possible stigma associated with reading within the learner group.

Statements like "I make fun of people who read a lot" with a mean of 2.44 and "I hate reading" with a mean of 2.56 received "Positive Attitude" interpretations, suggesting that although some learners harbor negative views, outright hostility or disdain for reading is not widespread. Moreover, the relatively low scores on statements like "I never check out a book from the library" with a mean of 2.62, and "I would rather have someone just tell me information" with a mean of 2.69 suggest that while some learners prefer avoiding reading, when possible, these behaviors are not universally strong.

In summary, learners display a moderate negative attitude toward reading, demonstrating some resistance to engaging with books, especially when reading is perceived as an obligation or time-consuming. However, the absence of extreme negativity suggests potential for improvement through interventions like Sustained Silent Reading (SSR), which could help shift these attitudes toward more positive reading experiences.

The data indicates a moderate negative attitude toward reading, reflecting some reluctance to engage with books, particularly when reading is viewed as a chore or a drain on time. Yet, the lack of severe negativity points to the possibility of enhancement through interventions like SSR, which can facilitate more positive reading experiences.

Supporting this, a study by David and Suan (2019) found that SSR significantly improved reading comprehension and fostered a more positive attitude toward reading among students with lower reading proficiency levels. By providing dedicated time for independent reading in a supportive environment, SSR can help learners rediscover the joy of reading and cultivate a more positive relationship with books.

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted the reading engagement of Grade 9 learners, creating a ripple effect that extends beyond the disruption of traditional classroom learning. The shift to modular distance learning has inadvertently hindered the development of strong reading habits and a genuine love for literature. The lack of consistent interaction with teachers and peers has diminished the social and motivational aspects of reading, rendering it less enjoyable for some students. The absence of hands-on activities, such as group reading projects or interactive reading games, has limited opportunities for dynamic exploration of the written word.

Furthermore, the emotional and psychological impacts of the pandemic have also affected students' focus and motivation, potentially leading to a decline in their desire to read. It is crucial to address these challenges and find innovative ways to rekindle students' passion for reading in the post-pandemic era, ensuring that all learners could develop a lifelong love for reading.

Additionally, the rise of mobile games and social media has significantly distracted Grade 9 learners, contributing to their moderate attitude toward reading. While the pandemic has disrupted traditional learning environments, the constant allure of digital entertainment has inadvertently reduced the time and motivation students dedicate to reading. The accessibility of engaging games and social platforms has created a barrier to focusing on the quiet enjoyment of a good book, making it harder for students to find the time and mental space to immerse themselves in a story.

To confront these challenges, it is essential to implement targeted interventions that promote reading as a valuable and enjoyable activity. Programs such as Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) can provide structured time for students to read, allowing them to experience the pleasure and benefits of literature in a supportive environment.

Additionally, diversifying reading materials to include genres and formats that resonate with students' interests such as graphic novels, non-fiction, and digital content can further stimulate engagement. Encouraging peer discussions about books and creating platforms for sharing reading experiences can enhance social connections to reading, making it a more communal and enjoyable activity.

Ultimately, fostering a positive reading culture requires a multifaceted approach that not only acknowledges the current moderate attitudes but also actively seeks to transform them into a more enthusiastic and enduring love for reading. By addressing the identified gaps and leveraging students' existing interests, educators can cultivate a generation of lifelong readers who appreciate the value of literacy in their lives.

Table 3

The Results of Individual Learners' Observation Before the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading in Terms of Self and Peer Distraction

Observed Behavior	Frequency							
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8
The learner is...								
1. not actively refusing to participate	5	3	2	1	0	0	0	0
2. engaging in a brief, non-disruptive conversation with classmates	5	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
3. redirecting attention to the task after a conversation with classmates	3	2	2	1	0	0	0	0
4. occasionally tapping a foot	4	3	3	2	1	0	0	0
5. occasionally adjusting a chair	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6. arriving without essential materials	12	7	6	3	2	0	0	0
7. requiring reminders or assistance from the teacher to get ready	3	2	2	2	0	0	0	0
8. shifting frequently in the seat	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9. momentarily lapses in attention	7	5	5	4	3	1	0	0
10. lonely	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11. not excited	4	3	3	1	0	0	0	0
12. frequently losing focus	7	6	6	5	3	2	0	0
13. requiring repeated redirection	3	3	2	2	1	0	0	0
14. showing a lack of readiness for the reading session	15	12	12	10	8	5	2	0
15. showing a clear lack of enthusiasm for the reading activity	5	3	3	2	0	0	0	0
16. engaging in frequent and loud conversations that disrupt the entire class	10	7	5	3	1	0	0	0

The table portrays the results of the observation made by the teacher before the start of the reading session within eight- weeks of implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading.

As shown in the table, during the first week of implementation, 15 students (38.46%) exhibited a lack of readiness, 12 students (30.76%) arrived without essential materials, and 10 students (25.64%) engaged in frequent and loud conversations that disrupted the entire class. Meanwhile, 3 students (7.69%) redirected their attention to the task after talking with classmates, requiring reminders or assistance from the teacher to get ready and needing repeated redirection.

In the second week, 12 students (30.76%) still showed a lack of readiness, while 7 students (19.74%) arrived without essential materials and engaged in disruptive conversations. On the other hand, 2 students (5.12%) engaged in brief, non-disruptive conversations with classmates, redirecting their attention to the task afterward and requiring reminders or assistance from the teacher.

By the third week of implementation, 12 students (30.76%) continued to show a lack of readiness, 6 students (15.38%) arrived without essential materials, and 5 students (12.82%) were engaged in frequent and loud conversations that disrupted the class.

Additionally, 2 students (5.12%) were not actively refusing to participate; they engaged in brief, non-disruptive conversations with classmates, redirected their attention to the task after these conversations, required reminders or assistance from the teacher, and needed repeated directions.

In the fourth week, 10 students (25.64%) showed a lack of readiness, and 5 students (12.82%) frequently lost focus. There was also 1 student (2.56%) who was not actively refusing to participate, redirected their attention to the task after a conversation with a classmate, and was not excited about the activity.

During the fifth week of implementation, 8 students (20.51%) showed a lack of readiness, and 3 students (7.69%) frequently or momentarily lost focus. Additionally, 1 student (2.56%) was occasionally tapping their foot, required repeated directions from the teacher, and engaged in loud conversations that disrupted the entire class. In the sixth and seventh weeks of the program, 5 students (12.82%) and 2 students (5.12%), respectively, exhibited a lack of readiness. Only 1 student (2.56%) in the seventh week had momentary lapses in attention. By the last week of implementation, students showed no signs of self- or peer-destructive behavior.

These observation results indicate that the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) Program significantly improved students' attitudes toward reading activities. Their readiness improved from nearly 4 in every 10 students in the initial week to none in the eighth week.

Additionally, students learned the importance of bringing essential materials such as notebooks, paper, and pens to the reading activity. The reading sessions also helped discipline students regarding conversations with their classmates, reducing disruptions in the class. Furthermore, the absence of self- and peer distractions in the final week

demonstrates considerable improvement in students' attitudes toward reading activities, suggesting that consistency is a key factor in this progress.

Although it is common for students to be hesitant to participate and exhibit undesirable behaviors in the first week of implementation, many may view the reading sessions as an additional burden to their academic responsibilities. They might feel unhappy about their frustration level, which is why they were included as participants in the program. However, after eight weeks of implementing the SSR Program, students' negative perceptions changed.

This further implies that the SSR Program effectively developed students' attitudes toward reading. It helped eliminate various disruptive behaviors, whether self-induced or through interaction with classmates. These positive indications suggest that this program should be continuously implemented with the same group of students and expanded to other grade levels. School heads and stakeholders should also actively participate in this program to enhance its effectiveness and availability for all learners.

Table 4
The Results of Individual Learners' Observation Before the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading Using Various Reading Materials in Terms of Self-Engagement.

Observed Behavior	Frequency							
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8
The learner is...								
1. participating in pre-reading activities	3	9	12	18	21	28	30	39
2. brings necessary materials	15	21	28	35	39	39	39	39
3. Make a basic attempt to organize their reading space	2	7	8	12	15	21	30	35
4. showing some enthusiasm for the topic or the reading materials	4	12	15	20	25	30	34	39
5. making multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences	0	7	11	19	20	32	35	37
6. showing confidence and seem prepared with the activity they are going to do	0	6	9	16	21	24	30	32
7. showing curiosity by asking questions about the text	2	4	7	7	12	15	16	20
8. volunteering to answer questions	2	3	7	10	20	25	32	36
9. volunteering to share thoughts	1	3	5	10	14	18	21	22
10. expressing genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the topic or reading material	3	7	15	21	27	30	39	39
11. paying close attention during pre-reading activities and discussions	7	11	18	24	30	32	37	39

The table presents the results of the observations made by teachers before the start of the reading sessions each week during the eight-week implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) Program, utilizing different reading materials in terms of self-engagement. During the first week of implementation, 15 learners (38.46%) brought the necessary materials, while 7 learners (17.95%) paid close attention to the pre-reading activities and discussions. Meanwhile, 2 learners (5.12%) made basic attempts to organize their reading spaces and showed curiosity by asking questions.

In the following week, 21 students (53.85%) were able to bring the necessary materials; 12 students (30.77%) demonstrated some enthusiasm for the topics or reading materials; and 11 students (28.21%) paid close attention to the pre-reading activities and discussions. Conversely, only 4 students (10.26%) out of 39 showed curiosity by asking questions, and 3 students (7.69%) volunteered to share their thoughts.

During the third week, 28 students (71.79%) brought the necessary materials; 18 students (46.15%) paid close attention to the pre-reading activities and discussions; and 15 students (38.46%) expressed genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the topics or reading materials. However, only 5 students (12.82%) volunteered to share their thoughts. In the fourth week, 35 students (89.74%) brought the necessary materials; 24 students (61.54%) paid close attention to the pre-reading activities and discussions; and 21 students (53.85%) expressed genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the reading activities. Only 7 students (17.95%) showed curiosity by asking questions about the topic.

In the fifth week, 39 students (100%) brought the necessary materials; 30 students (76.92%) paid close attention to the pre-reading activities and discussions; and 27 students (69.23%) expressed genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the reading activities. However, only 12 students (30.77%) showed curiosity by asking questions about the topic. During the sixth week, 39 students (100%) brought the necessary materials; 32 students (82.05%) paid close attention to the pre-reading activities and discussions and made connections to prior knowledge and experiences; and 30 students (76.92%) expressed genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the reading activities. Only 12 students (30.77%) showed curiosity by asking questions about the topic. In the seventh week, all 39 students (100%) brought materials and expressed genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the activity, with 37 students (94.87%) paying close attention.

By the last week, all 39 students (100%) participated in the pre-reading activities, brought the necessary materials, expressed genuine excitement and enthusiasm, and paid close attention to the pre-reading activities.

The results of the teacher observations indicate a gradual change in students' attitudes and behaviors before the start of the reading sessions. The number of students exhibiting self-engagement behaviors increased over the weeks of implementation, demonstrating a significant improvement in the attitudes of the 39 students. A notable improvement was seen in the bringing of necessary materials for the reading activities;

during the first two weeks, a majority of students failed to bring the required materials, suggesting a lack of interest in the reading activities. By the final week, all students actively participated in pre-reading activities, and their excitement and enthusiasm for answering teachers' questions significantly increased.

These observations indicate that the SSR Program effectively engaged students in reading activities. Additionally, the efforts of teachers to assist struggling readers have proven beneficial. However, teachers should pay attention to learners who do not voluntarily share their thoughts, as they may require support to build their confidence in expressing their ideas. Encouraging voluntary participation is preferable to calling on students or forcing them to share their feelings and thoughts about the topics they read.

This further implies that the reading program should be implemented consistently, as it serves its intended purpose. School heads should provide technical assistance to teachers to ensure that all activities are carried out as planned. Additionally, programs like this should be designed for students at independent and instructional reading levels. Teachers and schools should not overlook these students, as they have their own needs and challenges in reading that must be addressed as soon as possible.

Table 5
The Results of Individual Learner's Observation Before the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading in terms of Peer Engagement

Observed Behavior	Frequency							
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8
The learner is...								
1. working individually on pre-reading activities	32	17	15	12	8	0	0	0
2. not actively seeking for help	25	17	15	8	8	0	0	0
3. not actively seeking feedback from peers	35	32	27	24	15	8	7	4
4. showing not much enthusiasm for collaborating	37	30	16	15	7	0	0	0
5. not actively defining shared goals with peers	32	25	24	21	16	8	4	2
6. actively listening to others' perspective	4	8	12	20	27	28	31	35
7. asking occasional questions to peers about the reading activity	4	6	12	12	10	14	15	14
8. sharing reading material and information with a classmate	5	12	16	20	20	23	25	30
9. having a general idea of what he/she hopes to learn from the reading activities	4	10	19	25	34	34	35	36
10. engaging in conversations with classmates	10	12	21	24	32	39	39	39
11. sharing ideas with classmates	0	3	8	15	23	24	28	30
12. working in pairs or small groups on pre/post-reading activities	5	10	18	24	30	39	39	39
13. supporting each other's ideas	0	5	12	19	21	24	25	25
14. seeking clarifications with classmates	0	3	5	6	12	15	12	13

15. engaging in lively discussions with classmates sharing ideas	0	4	10	15	19	20	24	30
16. working effectively in groups on pre/post-reading activities	10	15	21	25	30	33	36	39
17. expressing genuine excitement and enthusiasm for the topic or reading material	4	10	15	18	24	25	30	31
18. having a strong desire to work together	4	12	15	20	28	32	35	36

The table presents the results of the observations conducted by the teacher at the start of the reading sessions with 39 students, focusing on self and peer engagement. In the first week of implementation, the teacher noted that 35 students (89.74%) did not ask for feedback from peers; 33 students (84.62%) showed little enthusiasm for working with classmates; and 30 students (76.92%) were not actively defining shared goals with partners. Only 2 students (5.12%) shared ideas with classmates, and 5 students (12.82%) actively listened to others' perspectives and occasionally asked questions.

In the following week, 32 students (82.05%) still did not seek feedback from peers; 30 students (76.92%) showed limited enthusiasm for collaboration; and 25 students (64.10%) were not actively defining shared goals with their peers. Meanwhile, only 3 students (7.69%) shared ideas with classmates and sought clarification.

By the third week, 27 students (69.23%) were not actively seeking feedback; 24 students (61.54%) were not sharing their goals with peers; and 21 students (53.85%) engaged in conversations with classmates, effectively working in groups on pre-reading activities. Additionally, 5 students (12.82%) sought clarifications from classmates, while 8 students (20.51%) shared ideas.

In the fourth week, 25 students (64.10%) expressed ideas about what they hoped to learn during the reading activities; 24 students (61.54%) were still not seeking feedback but engaged in conversations with classmates and worked in small groups or pairs during pre-reading activities. There were 6 students (15.38%) seeking clarifications from their classmates, while 8 students (20.51%) did not ask for help.

By the fifth week, before the reading session, 34 students (87.18%) had a general idea of what they hoped to learn from the reading activities; 32 students (82.05%) were having conversations with their classmates; and 30 students (76.92%) were working in pairs or small groups on pre-reading activities. Meanwhile, only 8 students (20.51%) worked individually during pre-reading activities, did not actively seek help, and showed little enthusiasm for collaboration.

In the sixth week, all 39 students (100%) engaged in conversations with their classmates and worked in pairs or small groups on pre-reading activities. Furthermore, 34 students (87.18%) had a general idea of what they hoped to learn from reading. However, 8 students (20.51%) did not ask for feedback from classmates and did not actively define shared goals with peers.

During the seventh week of implementation, all 39 students (100%) were engaged in conversations with their classmates and working in pairs or small groups on pre-reading activities. Additionally, 35 students (89.74%) had a general idea of what they hoped to learn from reading and expressed a strong desire to work together.

Furthermore, 36 students (92.31%) worked effectively in groups to accomplish pre-reading activities. However, 7 students (17.95%) did not ask for feedback from classmates, and 4 students (10.26%) did not actively define shared goals with peers.

In the last week of implementation, all 39 students (100%) worked effectively in pairs, small groups, and large groups to complete pre-reading activities and engaged in conversations with their classmates. Additionally, 36 students (92.31%) had a general idea of what they hoped to learn from the reading activities and expressed a strong desire to collaborate. On the other hand, 4 students (10.26%) did not ask for feedback from classmates, and 2 students (5.13%) did not actively define shared goals with peers.

The results of the observations conducted before the start of the reading sessions over eight weeks demonstrate significant changes in peer engagement due to the implemented program. During the first week, students tended to work independently, often overlooking the benefits of collaborating with their peers. While only a small percentage of students engaged in conversations and collaboration in the initial weeks, this behavior improved over time. Students began working together in pairs and groups, leveraging the advantages of collaboration to achieve the goals of their reading activities. They also learned to listen to their classmates' ideas and opinions and gained a clearer vision of what they wanted to learn during the implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading Program.

This further implies that programs like Sustained Silent Reading need to be consistently implemented to achieve their objectives. School heads, teachers, and other stakeholders should work collaboratively to enhance the program's effectiveness. Additionally, a Sustained Silent Reading Program should be implemented for learners with frustrated reading levels and other reading challenges.

Part II. The Learner's Attitude Towards Reading After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading

Table 6

The Learner's Attitude Towards Reading After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading (Positive)

Reading Attitude (Positive)	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I have lots of books at home.	4.23	Highly Positive Attitude	13
2. I like to read a book whenever I have free time.	4.74	Highly Positive Attitude	2
3. I get excited about books I have read.	4.74	Highly Positive Attitude	3
4. I love to read.	4.77	Highly Positive Attitude	1
5. I like to read books by well-known authors.	4.74	Highly Positive Attitude	4
6. I like to stay at home and read.	4.54	Highly Positive Attitude	8
7. I like to read to escape from problems.	4.51	Highly Positive Attitude	9
8. I like to share books with my friends.	4.44	Highly Positive Attitude	12
9. I generally check out a book whenever I'm in the library.	4.67	Highly Positive Attitude	5
10. I like to broaden my interests through reading.	4.46	Highly Positive Attitude	11
11. I read a lot.	4.67	Highly Positive Attitude	6
12. I like to improve my vocabulary to use more words.	4.67	Highly Positive Attitude	7
13. I like to get books for gifts.	4.49	Highly Positive Attitude	10
Grand Mean	4.59	Highly Positive Attitude	

Table 6 reveals a significant improvement in learners' attitudes toward reading following the implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program, as evidenced by the grand mean score of 4.59, reflecting a highly positive attitude overall. This marks a substantial shift from the moderate attitudes displayed before the SSR intervention, demonstrating that the program has fostered a more enthusiastic and engaged reading culture among the learners.

The statement "I love to read," with a mean of 4.77, ranks highest, indicating that strong enjoyment of reading was cultivated through the SSR program. Similarly, statements such as "I like to read a book whenever I have free time," with a mean of 4.74 (ranked 2), and "I get excited about books I have read," also with a mean of 4.74 (ranked 3), indicate that learners now view reading as a pleasurable and exciting activity. These findings reflect a significant positive transformation in their engagement with books.

The learners also showed a heightened appreciation for reading habits and behaviors, such as "I generally check out a book when I go to the library" with a mean of 4.67 and "I like to improve my vocabulary so I can use more words" with a mean of 4.67, both of which indicate that reading has become a more integral part of their lives. Even lower-ranked items like "I have lots of books at home" with a mean of 4.23 and "I like to

share books with my friends” with a mean of 4.44 still demonstrate highly positive attitudes, suggesting that the learners' relationship with reading has improved across various dimensions.

Overall, the highly positive attitudes displayed in all 13 statements suggest that the SSR program has been highly effective in increasing learners' enthusiasm for reading and encouraging more consistent and meaningful engagement with books. This transformation indicates that sustained reading initiatives, paired with access to diverse reading materials, can significantly improve learners' attitudes toward reading, making it a more enjoyable and valued activity in their daily lives.

The positive transformation observed in learners' attitudes toward reading underscores the significance of sustained reading initiatives paired with access to diverse reading materials. These elements are crucial for fostering a positive reading culture and promoting a lifelong love for reading. The data demonstrate how such initiatives can effectively address the challenges associated with negative attitudes toward reading and cultivate a more positive and engaged reading experience.

In support of this, a study by Anderson (2023) found that SSR significantly improved reading comprehension and fostered a more positive attitude toward reading among students with lower reading proficiency levels. By providing dedicated time for independent reading and fostering a supportive environment, SSR can help learners discover the joy of reading and develop a more positive relationship with books.

Table 7

The Learner’s Attitude Towards Reading After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading (Negative)

Reading Attitude(negative)	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
14. I feel I have better things to do than read.	1.79	Highly Positive Attitude	2
15. I seldom buy a book.	1.85	Positive Attitude	1
16. I am willing to tell people that I do not like to read.	1.74	Highly Positive Attitude	3
17. I never check out a book from the library.	1.69	Highly Positive Attitude	4
18. I seldom read except when I have to do a book report.	1.56	Highly Positive Attitude	10
19. I think reading is a waste of time.	1.38	Highly Positive Attitude	12
20. I think reading is boring.	1.56	Highly Positive Attitude	11
21. I think people are strange when they read a lot.	1.69	Highly Positive Attitude	5
22. I make fun of people who read a lot.	1.69	Highly Positive Attitude	6
23. I would rather someone tell me information so I won't have to read to get it.	1.62	Highly Positive Attitude	9
24. I hate reading.	1.64	Highly Positive Attitude	8
25. It takes me a long time to read a book.	1.67	Highly Positive Attitude	7
Grand Mean	1.66	Highly Positive Attitude	

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Very Low Attitude

3.41-4.20- Low Attitude
2.61-3.40-Moderate Attitude
1.81-2.60- Positive Attitude
1.00-1.80-Highly Positive Attitude

The table illustrates learners' negative attitudes toward reading after the implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program. The grand mean of 1.66, interpreted as a highly positive attitude, indicates a substantial reduction in negative perceptions of reading, demonstrating the program's success in minimizing negative views and reluctance toward reading.

The highest-ranked negative attitude, "I seldom buy a book," with a mean of 1.85, still reflects a positive attitude rather than a completely negative one. This suggests that while learners may not frequently purchase books, this behavior is less indicative of their overall reading engagement. Other statements, such as "I feel I have better things to do than read," with a mean of 1.79, and "I am willing to tell people that I do not like to read," with a mean of 1.74, demonstrate similarly low levels of negativity, signifying that learners now place more value on reading compared to other activities.

More striking are the low scores for items like "I think reading is a waste of time," with a mean of 1.38 (ranking 12), and "I think reading is boring," with a mean of 1.56 (ranking 11). These indicate that after the SSR program, learners overwhelmingly reject the notion that reading is uninteresting or unproductive. Similarly, the statement "I hate reading," with a mean of 1.64, reveals that extreme dislike for reading has significantly decreased among learners. Even traditionally negative views, such as "I make fun of people who read a lot," and "I think people are strange when they read a lot," both with a mean of 1.69, are now held by very few learners, indicating a shift in the social perception of readers within the group.

Overall, the scores across all negative attitude statements suggest that the SSR program is effective in developing a positive attitude toward reading while significantly reducing negative perceptions. Learners no longer view reading as boring, a waste of time, or something to be avoided, highlighting the program's success in reshaping their mindset toward reading as an enjoyable and valuable activity.

The success of the SSR program serves as a compelling example of how targeted interventions can effectively address the complexities of reading attitudes and foster a genuine appreciation for the transformative power of literature. The positive outcomes observed in this case provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers seeking to promote a love for reading among learners.

Supporting this, a study by Azhar and Hartanto (2022) found that SSR, when implemented with a diverse range of reading materials, effectively promoted a love for reading among students. This study emphasized the importance of providing students with choices in their reading materials, allowing them to explore genres and topics that resonate with their interests. By offering a variety of books, educators can cater to individual preferences and foster a more engaging and enjoyable reading experience.

This aligns with the observed positive attitudes in the current data, suggesting that the SSR program, coupled with access to diverse reading materials, has been instrumental in fostering a more positive and engaging reading culture among learners.

Table 8

The Results of Individual Learners' Observation After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading Using Various Reading Materials in Terms of Self and Peer Distraction

Observed Behavior	Frequency							
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8
The learner is...								
1. refusing to participate	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	0
2. engaging in a brief, non-disruptive conversation with classmates	4	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
3. redirecting attention to the task after a conversation with classmates	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	0
4. occasionally tapping a foot	3	2	2	1	1	0	0	0
5. occasionally adjusting a chair	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6. shifting frequently in the seat	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7. momentarily lapses in attention	6	4	4	3	2	0	0	0
8. lonely	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9. not excited	4	3	2	0	0	0	0	0
10. frequently losing focus	6	6	5	4	2	1	0	0
11. requiring repeated redirection	3	2	2	1	1	0	0	0
12. showing a lack of readiness for the post-reading activities	13	12	10	9	7	3	0	0
13. showing a lack of enthusiasm to participate in the post-reading activity	4	3	2	1	0	0	0	0
14. engaging in loud conversations that disturbed the entire class	9	6	5	3	0	0	0	0

Table 8 displays the results of the observations conducted by the teacher after each reading session during the eight-week implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program, focusing on self and peer disruptive behavior. As shown in the table, during the first week of implementation, 13 students (33.33%) demonstrated a lack of readiness; 9 students (23.08%) engaged in frequent and loud conversations that disrupted the entire class; and 6 students (15.38%) momentarily and frequently lost attention and focus. Meanwhile, 2 students (5.13%) redirected their attention to the task after conversing with classmates, while 3 students (7.69%) required reminders or assistance from the teacher to get ready, needing repeated redirection.

In the second week of post-reading activities, 12 students (30.76%) exhibited a lack of readiness; 6 students (15.38%) engaged in loud conversations that disrupted the class; and many frequently lost focuses. On the other hand, 2 students (5.12%) engaged in brief, non-disruptive conversations with classmates, redirecting their attention back to the task after these interactions, while also requiring reminders or assistance from the teacher and tapping their feet.

By the third week of implementation, 10 students (25.64%) showed a lack of readiness; 5 students (12.82%) engaged in frequent and loud conversations that disrupted the class, while also frequently losing focus. Additionally, 1 student (2.56%) refused to participate, and 2 students (5.12%) engaged in brief, non-disruptive conversations with classmates, redirected their attention to the task after talking, required reminders or assistance from the teacher, needed repeated directions, occasionally tapped their feet, and exhibited a lack of enthusiasm.

In the fourth week, 9 students (23.08%) showed a lack of readiness, and 4 students (10.26%) frequently lost focus. Additionally, there was 1 student (2.56%) who redirected their attention to the task after a conversation with classmates, showed little excitement about the activity, tapped their foot, required repeated redirection, and exhibited a lack of enthusiasm for participating in the post-reading activities.

During the fifth week of implementation, 7 students (17.95%) showed a lack of readiness, while 1 student (2.56%) occasionally tapped their foot, required repeated directions from the teacher, and displayed a lack of enthusiasm for participating in the post-reading activities. In the sixth week, 3 students (7.69%) exhibited a lack of readiness, and 1 student (5.12%) frequently lost focus.

During the final weeks of implementation, students showed no signs of self-destructive or peer-destructive behavior following the SSR program. The findings from these observations demonstrated a significant improvement in students' attitudes toward reading sessions on a weekly basis. In the first week of post-reading activities, 1 in every 3 students was unprepared to participate in class activities, such as exchanging ideas, answering questions, and sharing related experiences. However, this number gradually decreased over the following weeks, until the last two weeks when all students were prepared for any potential post-reading activities. Furthermore, learners recognized the importance of bringing necessary supplies, such as notebooks, paper, and pens.

Another common disruptive behavior noted was students engaging in loud conversations that disturbed the entire class. The number of students exhibiting this behavior decreased until the fifth week, at which point none displayed this behavior anymore. The reading exercises also helped students maintain their composure while conversing, minimizing disruptions to the entire class. The fact that students were not distracted by others or themselves in the final week indicates a significant improvement in their attitudes toward reading activities. Consistency may have played a key role in this improvement.

Initially, it is common for students to exhibit inappropriate behaviors related to the program and to be somewhat reluctant to participate during the first week of implementation. They may perceive the reading assignment as additional work on top of an already demanding academic schedule and feel frustrated about being included in the program. However, after eight weeks of implementation, students' negative thoughts were altered, as they recognized the benefits gained from the reading program.

These observations suggest that the Sustained Silent Reading Program effectively improves students' attitudes toward reading. It boosts learners' confidence in sharing insights related to the stories they read and allows them to expand their knowledge by asking questions to the teacher and their classmates. These findings indicate that the same set of students across multiple grade levels should regularly participate in such programs.

Table 9

The Results of Individual Learners' Observation After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading in Terms of Self-Engagement

Observed Behavior	Frequency							
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8
The learner is...								
1. participating in post-reading activities	6	10	15	20	25	28	32	39
2. doing individual post-reading activities silently and alone	30	21	12	8	5	0	0	0
3. answering questions about the story read when called by the teacher	30	25	17	12	7	3	3	0
4. making multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences	5	9	15	19	28	33	35	38
5. exhibiting confidence in participating in the post-reading activities	4	7	12	17	22	29	30	35
6. raising own questions about the story read	3	5	7	10	13	15	19	25
7. volunteering to answer questions	0	3	8	14	22	27	35	39
8. volunteering to share thoughts and ideas about the text/ story read	2	4	8	12	16	20	21	27
9. paying close attention during post-reading activities and discussions	9	14	20	26	30	34	37	39

Table 9 displays the results of the observations during post-reading activities in terms of self-engagement. The table reveals that in the first week of implementation, 30 students (76.92%) engaged in post-reading activities silently and independently, and the same number of students answered questions about the story read when called upon.

Meanwhile, 2 students (5.13%) volunteered to share thoughts and ideas about the text or story, and 3 students (7.69%) raised questions regarding the story read. During the second week's post-reading activities, 25 students (64.10%) responded to questions when called upon by the instructor, 21 students (53.85%) completed post-reading tasks silently, and 14 students (35.90%) paid attentive attention to the activities. However, only 3 students (7.69%) volunteered to answer questions, and 4 students (10.26%) shared their thoughts and ideas on the text or story read voluntarily.

Moreover, during the third week of post-reading activities, 20 students (51.28%) were paying close attention to the discussions; 17 students (43.59%) answered when called by the teacher; and 15 students (38.46%) participated in post-reading activities while making multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences. Meanwhile, 7 students (17.95%) raised questions, and 8 students (20.51%) volunteered to answer questions and share their thoughts and ideas about the text or story read.

In the fourth week of post-reading activities, 26 students (66.67%) were paying close attention to the discussions; 20 students (51.28%) participated in all activities; and 19 students (48.72%) made connections to prior knowledge and experiences. However, 8 students (20.51%) engaged in post-reading activities silently and alone.

During the fifth week, 30 students (76.92%) paid close attention to post-reading activities and discussions; 28 students (71.79%) made multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences; and 25 students (61.10%) participated in all activities. There were 7 students (17.95%) who answered questions only when called upon, and 5 students (12.82%) who engaged in post-reading activities silently and alone.

In the following week, 34 students (87.13%) were paying close attention to post-reading activities and discussions; 33 students (84.62%) made multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences; and 29 students (74.36%) exhibited confidence in participating in the post-reading activities. However, 3 students (7.69%) answered questions only when called upon, and 15 students (38.46%) raised questions.

By the seventh week of the program, 37 students (94.87%) were paying close attention to post-reading activities and discussions; 35 students (89.74%) made multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences; and 32 students (82.05%) participated in all post-reading activities. However, 3 students (7.69%) answered questions only when called, and 19 students (38.46%) raised their questions.

In the final week of implementation, 39 students (100.00%) were paying close attention to post-reading activities and discussions; they volunteered to answer questions and participated in all post-reading activities. Additionally, 38 students (97.44%) made multiple connections to prior knowledge and experiences. None of the students engaged in post-reading activities alone or answered questions only when called upon by the teachers.

This suggests a possible initial hesitancy or lack of confidence in expressing thoughts and ideas openly. The limited number of students volunteering contributions reflects this reserved engagement. However, a gradual but noticeable shift occurs over the subsequent weeks. While a considerable number of students continued to participate passively, the proportion steadily decreased. Simultaneously, there's a marked increase in the number of students actively raising questions and volunteering contributions. This indicates a growing comfort level and willingness to engage more actively with the material and share their interpretations.

By the sixth week, a significant transformation is evident. The overwhelming majority of students demonstrate active engagement, paying close attention, making connections to prior knowledge, and confidently participating in discussions. The near-total absence of passive participation (students working silently or only responding when called upon) in the final week strongly suggests that the SSR program successfully fostered a more proactive and confident learning environment.

The data implies that the SSR program's design effectively encouraged a shift from passive to active learning. The gradual increase in active participation suggests that the program, perhaps through modeling, discussion prompts, or a supportive classroom atmosphere, gradually empowered students to feel more confident in expressing their thoughts and ideas. The near-universal active engagement by the final week strongly indicates that this positive change is a lasting effect of the program, highlighting the potential of SSR to cultivate independent, confident, and engaged readers. The findings underscore the importance of creating a supportive learning environment that encourages active participation and fosters a love of reading.

The results of the observations conducted after the reading sessions during the eight-week duration of the Sustained Silent Reading Program demonstrate its effectiveness in enhancing the behavior and attitudes of Grade 9 students toward reading activities, particularly in terms of self-engagement.

The first notable improvement is in the participation rate of the students. During the initial three weeks, some students merely listened and watched their classmates during post-reading activities. However, as the implementation progressed, all students began to participate in these activities. There was also a significant increase in students raising their hands and volunteering to answer questions about the story, even without being called by the teacher, which indicates they were paying attention to the post-reading activities.

These improvements are particularly important for students at the frustration level, as they can boost their confidence and motivation regarding the value of reading. This, in turn, may lead to habitual reading activities even after the program has concluded.

Additionally, students learned to raise questions about the stories they read and sought clarification or shared their insights with the group. This suggests that higher-order thinking skills were also developed, as students at the frustration level typically know how to answer factual (wh-) questions but often struggle with implied questions.

Table 10

The Results of Individual Learner's Observation After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading in terms of Peer Engagement

Observed Behavior	Frequency							
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8
The learner is...								
1. working individually on post-reading activities	22	17	13	10	6	4	1	0
2. not actively seeking for help	24	16	15	8	7	3	0	0
3. not actively seeking feedback from peers	35	32	27	24	10	8	7	2
4. showing not much enthusiasm for collaborating	33	31	26	14	9	2	0	0
5. actively listening to other's perspectives and ideas about the story read	5	9	15	23	27	28	32	35
6. asking occasional questions to peers about the reading activity	5	7	12	15	11	14	15	14
7. sharing reading material and information with a classmate	8	12	18	20	20	24	25	30
8. engaging in conversations with classmates during the discussions	10	18	24	25	30	39	39	39
9. sharing ideas with classmates through informal talk	2	4	12	17	24	33	28	30
10. working in pairs or small groups on post-reading activities	7	10	18	24	30	39	39	39
11. seeking clarifications with classmates	1	3	5	6	12	15	12	13
12. working effectively in big groups on post-reading activities	12	16	22	27	30	33	37	39
13. having a strong desire to work together on the post-reading activities	10	11	17	24	29	33	35	36

Table 10 presents the results of individual learners' observations following the Sustained Silent Reading Program, focusing on peer engagement during post-reading activities. As shown in the table, during the first week of post-reading activities, 35 students (89.74%) were not actively seeking help, and 33 students (84.62%) showed little enthusiasm for collaboration. In contrast, 1 student (2.56%) sought clarification from classmates, and 2 students (5.13%) shared ideas through informal discussions.

In the second week, 32 students (82.05%) were still not actively seeking help, and 31 students (79.49%) continued to show minimal enthusiasm for collaboration. However, 3 students (7.69%) sought clarification, and 4 students (10.26%) shared ideas with classmates informally.

During the third week of post-reading activities, 27 students (69.23%) were not actively seeking help, while 26 students (66.67%) showed little enthusiasm for collaboration. Nonetheless, 24 students (61.54%) engaged in conversations with

classmates during discussions. Additionally, 5 students (12.82%) sought clarification, and 12 students (30.77%) shared ideas informally and occasionally asked questions about the reading activity.

In the fourth week, 27 students (69.23%) worked effectively in large groups on post-reading activities; 25 students (66.10%) engaged in conversations during discussions; and 24 students (61.54%) were still not actively seeking help. However, they worked well in pairs or small groups, demonstrating a strong desire to collaborate. Meanwhile, 6 students (15.38%) sought clarification from classmates, and 8 students (20.51%) were not actively seeking help.

During the fifth week, 30 students (76.92%) engaged in conversations with classmates during discussions and effectively collaborated in pairs, small groups, and large groups on post-reading activities. Additionally, 29 students (74.36%) expressed a desire to work together. Conversely, 6 students (15.38%) worked individually, and 7 students (17.95%) did not seek help.

In the sixth week, all 39 students (100.00%) engaged in conversations with classmates during discussions and worked effectively in pairs and small groups. This was followed by effective collaboration in large groups, with 33 students (84.62%) expressing a strong desire to work together. Meanwhile, 2 students (5.13%) showed little enthusiasm, and 3 students (7.69%) did not actively ask for help.

The results from the seventh and eighth weeks of post-reading activities were similar to those of the sixth week. Again, 39 students (100.00%) engaged in conversations during discussions and worked effectively in pairs, small groups, and large groups during the final week of post-reading activities. However, 1 student (2.56%) worked individually, and 2 students (5.13%) did not seek feedback from classmates.

Concurrently, the number of students actively participating in peer discussions and seeking clarification from classmates steadily increased. This suggests that the SSR program, over time, fostered a growing comfort level and appreciation for collaborative learning. By the sixth and seventh weeks, a remarkable transformation occurred. Nearly all students (100%) engaged in peer discussions during post-reading activities, and the vast majority demonstrated a strong desire to collaborate in various group settings. The initial reluctance to seek help from peers had virtually disappeared. The few remaining students who worked independently or showed little enthusiasm likely represent individual learning preferences or other factors unrelated to the program's effectiveness.

This data strongly implies that the SSR program successfully cultivated a positive shift in students' attitudes towards peer interaction and collaborative learning. The gradual increase in collaborative behaviors suggests that the program's design, perhaps through modeling or structured activities, facilitated the development of these social and academic skills.

The sustained high levels of peer engagement in the later weeks indicate that this positive change was not merely temporary but rather a lasting outcome of the program. The findings highlight the importance of incorporating collaborative elements into reading programs and suggest that providing sufficient time and opportunities for interaction can significantly enhance the learning experience and foster a more positive classroom environment.

The results of the peer engagement observations during the eight-week duration of the Sustained Silent Reading Program indicate significant improvements in how learners interacted with their classmates. By the last week of implementation, independent work was nearly eliminated, and students recognized the value of seeking help from both classmates and teachers. Their level of enthusiasm for group work also increased.

It is essential for students to listen to their classmates' ideas and opinions, as this broadens their perspectives. The effectiveness of pair, small, and large group activities is crucial for enhancing peer engagement. Students should understand that they are not alone and that their classmates support them during reading activities.

Additionally, the findings suggest that for initiatives like Sustained Silent Reading to succeed, consistent implementation is key. To enhance program effectiveness, school leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders should collaborate. The Sustained Silent Reading Program should extend to accommodate various reading levels among secondary students, moving beyond any initial dissatisfaction.

Part III. Significant Difference in Learner's Attitudes Towards Reading Before and After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading

Table 11
Significant Difference in Learner's Attitudes Towards Reading Before and After the Implementation of Sustained Silent Reading

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	3.644	.068	-13.756	24	.000	-1.5031	.1093	-1.7286	-1.2776

Equal			-13.756	16.55	.000	-1.5031	.1093	-1.7341	-1.2721
variances not assumed				9					

Table 11 shows a significant difference in learners' attitudes toward reading before and after implementing the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program, as indicated by the t-test results for equality of means. Levene's test for equality of variances produced an F-value of 3.644 with a significance level of .068, suggesting that the assumption of equal variances holds since the p-value is greater than .05. The t-test results reveal a t-value of -13.756 and a significance (2-tailed) value of .000, indicating a highly significant difference between attitudes before and after SSR.

The mean difference of -1.5031 demonstrates that learners' attitudes improved significantly after the program, reflecting a shift from negative to more positive attitudes.

The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference, ranging from -1.7286 to -1.2776, confirms substantial improvement, as the interval does not include zero. Overall, these results provide strong evidence that the SSR program positively impacted learners' reading attitudes, transforming them from moderate or negative to highly positive.

This statistically significant difference reinforces qualitative observations from the data. The shift from moderate or negative attitudes to highly positive ones strongly suggests that the SSR program was instrumental in fostering a more enthusiastic reading culture among learners. This finding aligns with previous research highlighting the positive impact of SSR on students' attitudes toward reading. Studies have shown that SSR can increase enjoyment and motivation while developing reading habits, leading to more positive associations with reading.

In essence, the data powerfully demonstrated that the SSR program fostered a remarkable transformation in students' attitudes towards reading. What began as perhaps a lukewarm or even resistant stance towards reading blossomed into a considerably more enthusiastic and positive outlook. This success suggests that SSR holds significant promise as a valuable tool for cultivating a love of reading in students. Further research, including qualitative data gathering, could provide even richer insights into the reasons behind this positive transformation and help refine the program's implementation for even greater effectiveness.

Supporting this, a study by Manning and Dowd (2019) found that SSR significantly improved reading comprehension and fostered a more positive attitude toward reading among students with lower reading proficiency levels. By setting aside time for independent reading and creating a supportive environment, Sustained Silent Reading may help learners discover the joy of reading and develop a more positive connection with texts.

In conclusion, the results indicate that the SSR program had a positive impact on learners' reading attitudes. This significant transformation is a testament to the program's effectiveness in cultivating a more positive and engaged reading experience.

Part IV. Researcher's Recommended Implementation Plan to enrich Sustained Silent Reading as Reading Intervention Program

Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) is a vital component of a successful literacy program or intervention, recognized for its numerous benefits, including fostering a love for reading and enhancing comprehension skills. However, effective implementation can present unique challenges that require thoughtful strategies. With this, the researcher crafted and recommended an implementation plan to address these challenges while promoting student engagement and creating a positive reading attitude among Grade 9 learners in Bagupaye Integrated High School. By focusing on practical solutions for book selection, classroom management, and learner motivation, the researcher seeks to establish a sustainable SSR program that empowers learners to become confident, enthusiastic readers.

DISCUSSION

The study yielded the following findings:

1. The learner's attitude towards reading before the implementation of SSR?

1.1. In terms of Quantitative Data:

1.1.1. Before the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program, learners exhibited a moderate attitude toward reading, with a grand mean of 3.09. While some learners enjoyed activities such as improving vocabulary and developing a love for reading, their overall engagement remained moderate. They were not particularly enthusiastic about behaviors like checking out books from the library or sharing books with friends, indicating a need for improvement in fostering a stronger reading culture.

1.1.2. In terms of negative attitudes toward reading, learners demonstrated moderate negative sentiments, with a grand mean of 2.88. Many students felt they had better things to do than read or only read when required, such as for book reports. However, extreme negative views, such as hating reading or considering it a waste of time, were relatively low, suggesting that while reading was not a high priority, there was potential for change with the right intervention.

1.2. In terms of Qualitative Data:

1.2.1. In terms of self-distraction and engagement, observations made by the teacher before the start of the weekly reading sessions indicated that, at the beginning of the program's implementation, students were easily

distracted by themselves and their peers, resulting in low levels of engagement.

1.2.2. In terms of the peer distraction and engagement, during the final weeks of the program, self-distraction and peer distraction had diminished, and both self-engagement and peer engagement had significantly improved as learners transitioned from working individually to collaborating with classmates in pairs, small groups, and larger groups.

2. The learner's attitude towards reading after the implementation of SSR in terms of the following:

2.1. In Terms of Quantitative Data:

2.1.1. After implementing the SSR program, there was a marked improvement in learners' attitudes toward reading, reflected in a grand mean of 4.59. Students began to enjoy reading in their free time, expressed excitement about books, and recognized reading as a means to broaden their interests and improve their vocabulary. This shift indicates that the SSR program effectively promotes positive reading habits and enhances the enjoyment of reading among learners.

2.1.2. Negative attitudes toward reading significantly decreased following the SSR program, resulting in a grand mean of 1.66, indicating an overall negative sentiment. Learners largely dismissed the notion that reading is boring or a waste of time, and negative behaviors, such as mocking those who read frequently or feeling awkward about reading, were minimal. This reduction in negative attitudes underscores the success of SSR in transforming learners' perceptions of reading.

2.2. In Terms of Qualitative Data:

2.2.1. The results of the observations conducted after the reading sessions during the eight-week duration of the Sustained Silent Reading Program demonstrate its effectiveness in enhancing the behavior and attitudes of Grade 9 students toward reading activities, particularly regarding self-engagement.

2.2.2. Observations during the post-reading activities and the initial weekly reading sessions revealed that students were easily distracted at the program's start by themselves and their peers, leading to low levels of peer and self-engagement. Nevertheless, in the final weeks of the program's implementation, distractions diminished, and engagement levels increased as learners learned to collaborate effectively with their peers in various group settings.

3. The t-test results confirm a highly significant difference in learners' attitudes toward reading before and after SSR, with a p-value of .000 and a mean difference of -1.5031. This statistically significant improvement demonstrates that the SSR program had a substantial positive impact on learners' attitudes, effectively shifting them from moderate or negative perceptions to highly positive ones. The SSR initiative successfully enhanced the reading culture and enthusiasm among learners.
4. The implementation of Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) is essential for developing effective literacy programs, offering significant benefits such as fostering a love for reading and improving comprehension skills. However, successful implementation faces challenges that necessitate strategic planning. The proposed implementation plan aims to tackle these challenges by enhancing student engagement and cultivating a positive reading culture in schools. The plan aspires to create a sustainable SSR program that empowers learners to become confident and enthusiastic readers by prioritizing practical solutions related to book selection, classroom management, and student motivation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were proposed:

1. **Continue and Expand the SSR Program.** Given the strong positive impact observed, it is recommended that the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program be continued and expanded in schools to preserve and enhance students' reading habits and attitudes. Regular reading sessions can reinforce positive behaviors and sustain learners' enthusiasm for reading.

2. **Diverse Reading Materials.** To cater to various learner interests and keep reading enjoyable, schools should ensure that a wide variety of reading materials, including fiction, non-fiction, and diverse genres, are available to students. This will help maintain the momentum of the positive shift in attitudes.

3. **Encourage Reading Beyond Academics.** Schools and teachers should promote reading as an enjoyable activity beyond academic requirements. Organizing reading challenges, book clubs, or library visits could further foster a reading culture and sustain positive attitudes toward reading.

4. **Support for Struggling Readers.** While the overall attitude toward reading has improved, some learners may still need support in developing stronger reading skills. Identifying students who struggle with reading and providing targeted interventions or reading assistance will ensure that all learners benefit equally from the program.

5. **Create a Conducive Reading Environment.** Schools should establish an environment conducive to reading, such as comfortable reading spaces in classrooms

and libraries. A positive reading environment can encourage learners to read during their free time and help them develop lifelong reading habits.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The implementation of the Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) program had a significant positive impact on learners' attitudes toward reading. Before the SSR program, learners exhibited moderate positive and negative attitudes, showing some interest in reading while also demonstrating reluctance or indifference. However, after the implementation of SSR, there was a marked improvement, with learners displaying highly positive attitudes and significantly reducing their negative perceptions of reading.

The statistical analysis confirmed a significant difference in attitudes, affirming the effectiveness of the SSR program in fostering a more engaged and positive reading attitude among learners. These effects are also evident in the observations conducted by the teacher before the start of the weekly reading sessions and during the post-reading activities, where both self-distraction and peer distraction were eliminated, leading to enhanced self- and peer engagement in reading activities.

Consequently, the null hypothesis for the learner's attitude towards reading before and after the implementation of SSR is rejected, as there was a significant difference between the learner's attitude towards reading before and after the implementation of SSR.

Acknowledgments

Foremost, our GOD ALMIGHTY, the provider and source of all enlightenment and power, for giving the researcher knowledge, perseverance, hope, and determination to make this study possible.

To Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Chairperson of Extended Graduate Programs of Marinduque State College, for his untiring support, technical assistance, and continuous guidance to the researcher for this study to be a success;

To Dr. Gloria L. Ching, the researcher's adviser, for her valuable suggestions, guidance, and patience in checking this paper and for the enlightenment shared about the importance of this study;

To Sir Jerome L. Lingon, the researcher's editor, for his invaluable assistance in checking the language structure of this manuscript;

To Dr. Liza Manoos-Pacia, the researcher's statistician, for her exceptional statistical support and guidance, which were essential to the successful completion of this study.

To the chair and panel members, I would like to express my sincerest gratitude for their insightful contributions and invaluable feedback during the final defense. Their expertise and perspectives have significantly enriched this study.

To Ma'am Lailanie D. Formigones, the researcher's personal grammarian and editor, for her insightful guidance and dedication, which have significantly enhanced the quality of this research;

To Ms. Liezl M. Manoy; MarSU's Support Staff, Graduate School, for her unending moral support;

To Mr. and Mrs. De Luna, the researcher's parents for their constant encouragement and practical help throughout this challenging journey.

To Mr. Chris Anthony L. Ramos, Isaiah Thomas, Theo Izac, and Therese Epiphany, the researcher's spouse, and children for their unending care and love that inspired the researcher a lot to pursue this study;

To all great people whose names do not appear above for whatever assistance extended with sincerity, a million thanks to each of you.

REFERENCES

- Alayon, D.P. (2019). Utilizing SQ3R method in enhancing the reading proficiency of junior high school learners (unpublished master's thesis). National Teacher's College, Manila, Philippines.
- Anderson, A. M. (2023). Role of extensive reading habits in students' acquisition of composition writing skills in English in Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(30), 62-68.
- Anderson, T., Hiebert, R. Scott, N. A., & Wilkinson, (2021). Expectancy-Value Theory of Achievement Motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 69-81
- Armstrong, R., Mahar, Donna, & Abendroth, Mark. (2016). Sustained Silent Reading: A Vital Tool for Success in Secondary School, ProQuest Dissertations and Theses.
- Azhar, H. & Hartanto Y. (2022). Reading Difficulty and its Remediation: A Case Study. *European Journal of Educational Research* Volume 8, Issue 4, 1269 - 1286.
- Cain, D. & Oakhill, C. (2022). The Role of Reading Difficulties in the Associations between Task Values, Efficacy Beliefs, and Achievement Emotions. v32, pages1723–1746 retrieved September 28, 2022, from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11145-018-9922-x>
- Carrell, R. (2021). 'Explaining the Important Contribution of Reading Literacy to the Country's Generations: Indonesian's Perspectives', *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*
- Cho, N. & Krashen V. (2019). Newspaper reading habits of private university students: A case study on the world University of Bangladesh. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*. 12(1), 87-91. Retrieved from www.iosrjournals.org September 27, 2022.

- Cunningham, A. E. & Stanovich, K. F. (2019). A Longitudinal Study of the Development of Automatic Recognition Skills in Seventh Grade. *Journal of Reading Behavior*.
- David, R. & Suan, N. (2019). Online reading habits of university students in Bangladesh and its effects in ESL classroom. *International Journal of Education*, 4(30), 251-264.
- Deci, E. L. & Ryan, R. M. (1985). Self-determination Theory and the Facilitation of Intrinsic Motivation, Social Development, and Well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68–78.
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2002). Reading Literacy Program in the Elementary Schools (*DepEd Order No. 45, s. 2002*). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2002/04/DO_s2002_45.pdf
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2024). Department Memorandum No. 001, Series of 2024: Implementation of Catch-up Fridays. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2002/04/DM_s2024_001.pdf
- Enosh, T. Tzafir, A.N. & Stolovy, S. (2019). Silent Reading Fluency and Comprehension in Bilingual Children. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01265>
- Fetters, P. A. (2019). Assessment of reading problems among English language learners based , *Language and literacy development in bilingual settings* (pp. 304–334). The Guilford Press.
- Gardiner, A.R. (2021). Sustained Silent Reading: A Vital Tool for Success in Secondary School (Doctoral Dissertation). ProQuest Dissertations and Theses Global.
- Gelles, F. O., Watnik, O. A., & Perrin, O. M. (2021). A Survey on the Reading Habits among Colleges of Education Students in the Information Age. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(8). Retrieved September 27, 2022.
- Habagat, K. & Rizon, E. (2021) Elementary school-wide implementation of a blended learning program for reading intervention. *Journal of Educational Research*, 111(4), 497–506. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2017.1302914>
- Herman, G. et al. (2020). Matthew Effects in Reading: Some Consequences of Individual Differences in the Acquisition of Literacy. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 21(4), 360–407. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/files/u81/Stanovich1986.pdf>
- Manning, L. & Dowd, R. (2019). The Effect of Sustained Silent Reading on High School Students' Lexile Scores and Attitudes toward Reading. Retrieved September 28, 2022 from <https://www.edweek.org/policy-politics/no-child-left-behind-an-overview/2019/04https://youngreadersfoundation.org/importance-of-reading/>
- Maxwell, M. J. (2021). Reading in an alphasyllabary: Implications for a language universal theory of learning to read. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 16(5), 404–423. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2011.576352>
- McKenna, H. et al. (2021). Reading for pleasure: National Literacy Trust. Retrieved September 27, 2021, <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED496343.pdf>
- Miguel, M. A. (2021). Silent reading fluency and comprehension in bilingual children. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01265>
- Montalban, M. R. (2020). The Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on Reading Comprehension in Filipino Elementary Students. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 95(1), 12-25.

- National Book Development Board [NBDB], (2019). *NDP Reading Survey*. National Book Reading Development Board. <https://booksphilippines.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2019/12/2017-Readership-SurveyPublication.pdf>
- Organization For Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2018) *PISA 2018 Results: Volume I: What Students Know and Can Do*. OECD Publishing.
- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD]. (2022). Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018 Results (Volume I): What students know and can do. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>
- Perfetti, C.A. & Stafura, J. (2021). Word Knowledge in a Theory of Reading Comprehension. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 18(1), 22-37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2013.827687>
- Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) Results from PISA 2018. <https://www.gmanetwork.com/news/topstories/nation/717778/phl-ranks-lowest-out-of-79countries-in-reading-comprehension-global-survey/story/>
- Rintaningrum, G. (2019). On the Anglocentricities of Current Reading Research and Practice: The Perils of Overreliance on an "outlier" Orthography. *Psychological Bulletin*, 134(4), 584-615. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.134.4.584>
- Umali, M. (2016). *The Reading Difficulties of Grade III Pupils in District IV in the Schools Division of Manila*. Manila: Philippine College of Health Sciences, Inc.